

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: ITALY

Limnological research at the Science Museum of Trento: Biodiversity of extreme environments

Valeria Lencioni

Chief-Curator of the Invertebrate Zoology
and Hydrobiology Department,
Science Museum of Trento, Italy
Email: valeria.lencioni@muse.it

Most people are under the impression that entomologists working in a Natural History Museums spend their time managing dusty collections of insects, organizing events for class trips and the general public, teaching natural sciences to young students or working on exhibitions. Nowadays Natural History Museums are institutions dedicated to the documentation, protection, exploitation and valorization of natural and cultural diversity where entomologists in particular are at the forefront of environmental research. At least this is the mission of the MUSE, the Science Museum of Trento (Italy), previously Museo Tridentino di Scienze Naturali, the first museum in Italy that harmoniously blends nature, science and technology.

Fig. 1 Vedretta Lake (2600 m a.s.l.), Trentino, Italian Alps.

Fascinated by extreme habitats, with a background in limnology gained during my Masters' thesis twenty-five years ago I started to study the ecology of headwaters (springs, lakes and streams) in glaciated areas of the European Alps (Fig. 1), the Arctic (Fig. 2) and the Karakorum (Fig. 3), in Asia. A great adventure started at the Museo Tridentino di Scienze Naturali that offered a stimulating, smart and creative environment for young researchers, giving me the possibility to satisfy my curiosity of nature and passion for mountains, aquatic habitats and insects.

Within a team mainly represented by women, I climb peaks and glaciers to study the macroinvertebrate communities living in cold waters, from springs to ponds, lakes and streams (Fig. 4). Specifically, my main focus is on morphological, physiolog-

ical, phenological and genetic adaptation to cold in chironomids (Diptera Chironomidae), the most frequent and abundant taxon living in glacier-fed streams and other high altitude and latitude freshwater habitats, today threatened by extinction by climate change and pollution. Within the scenario of climate change, my attention has been devoted to studying the vulnerability and response of benthic communities to glacier retreat and the associated reduced discharge, increasing water temperatures and pollution. Changes in glacial biodiversity with an emphasis on macroinvertebrates, are approached holistically, with studies ranging from single genes to ecosystems. It is becoming increasingly clear that glaciers are a secondary source of pollution for the freshwaters they feed, acting as a temporary sink for many organic and inorganic pollutants that have been transported by the atmosphere from medium to long distances. Long-term studies coupled with experimental laboratory data are showing that wild populations of insects are suffering with evidence of local extinction of the most specialized cold hardy species such as *Diamesa steinboeckii*, the "ice fly" and other *Diamesa* species (Fig. 5).

Fig. 2 Bayelva glacier-fed stream (Svalbard Islands, Spitzbergen)

Specimens of this and all the cold hardy species collected in the Alps, Arctic and Karakorum are preserved in the MUSE's collections. Unlike universities and other public or private research and monitoring institutions, the museum stores collected organisms or parts of them (e.g. DNA vouchers) and therefore they remain available for studies of biogeography, ecology, and systematics to researchers of today and tomorrow. For instance, the MUSE maintains the biggest Italian collection of glacial insects, with over 800,000 specimens collected since 1996 (90% in ethanol and the rest as microscopic slides or pinned specimens) which will also be useful in the future in reconstructing the effects of today's environmental changes on biodiversity of mountain freshwaters.

The results of all our research activities find space in museum rooms and have been inspiring science cafés, interviews and workshops, to discuss sensitive issues like pharmaceutical pollution in running waters and to encourage sustainable behavior and environmental management.

Being a researcher in a Natural History Museum like MUSE gives me the opportunity to interact with other scientists, but also non-academic stakeholders and citizens through cutting-edge communications media. Museums offer a physical space that is ideal for knowledge transfer that is rooted in scientific research centered on documenting nature and its changes, but spreads its branches not only to the local community where research is conducted, but to all interested in biodiversity and the challenges it faces.

Photo by L. Latella

Fig. 3 Rakapochi Glacier, Bagrot Valley, Karakorum, Pakistan, taken from an altitude of 4500 m a.s.l.

Some Recent Publications

Lencioni V, Rodriguez-Prieto A, Allegrucci G. 2021. Congruence between molecular and morphological systematics of Alpine non-biting midges (Chironomidae, Diamesinae). *Zoologica Scripta* 50(4): 455-472.

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Bernabò P, Viero G, Lencioni V. 2020. A long noncoding RNA acts as a post-transcriptional regulator of heat shock protein (HSP70) synthesis in the cold hardy *Diamesa tonsa* under heat shock. *PLoS ONE* 15(4): e0227172.

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<https://www.muse.it>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4889854>

Photo by D. Debiasi

Fig. 4 Sampling of adult chironomids at the front of the Agola Glacier, Trentino, Italian Alps (2596 m a.s.l.) by the author.

Photo by F. Pupin

Fig. 5 *Diamesa zernyi* adult on the snowpack.